

130. Kewa

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Lit.: Franklin, K. J. (1971). "A Grammar of Kewa, New Guinea".

Note: - Franklin uses in his orthography /a/ instead of /' / (Schwa) and /aa/ instead of /a/
- high tones are marked with ' , low tones are unmarked

1. Segmental Properties

1.1 Phonotactic Patterns

- any V may follow any C
 - + exception: *yi, *yu, *wu
- low non-central and high vowels cannot occur in contiguous syllables separated by a consonant within the same morpheme
 - + no *CeCi, *CeCu, *CoCi, *CoCu

1.2 Phonological Processes

- some kind of vowel harmony applies when certain tense suffixes are attached to the stems
e.g. *ri-to* > *ritu*
carry-1sPF
"I have carried"

1.3 Default Syllable Template

- any C or V is possible as syllable onset
- only open syllables
- no minimal word requirement, e.g. *e* "garden", *u* "sleep"

2. Prosodic Properties

2.1 Stress

- stress is on first syllable if noun stem has less than four syllables
- stress is on the second syllable if noun stem has at least four syllables
- except for /aa/, long vowels are restricted to monosyllabic phonological feet
- phonological foot is unit of stress placement
 - + stress is on nucleus of phonological foot

2.2 Tone

- TBU is word

- four patterns: H, L, LH, HL
- patterns which consist solely of basic high tones cause perturbation of most patterns which are adjacent

2.2.1 Assimilation

- Rule 1: stems with basic LH are not perturbed
 - + LH doesn't perturb in nouns
 - + LH perturbs in verbs to LL only when preceded by negative clitic *-na* (which has a basic low tone)
- Rule 2: progressive assimilation to lows
 - + when free pronouns with basic L are followed by verb stems, the verb stems become completely L
 - e.g. *ne sá-li* > *ne sali*
 2Sg put-2sFUT
 "you will put it"
 - + exception: LH verb stems (see Rule 1) and compound stems
 - e.g. *nimi yalá-mé* > *nimi yalámé*
 2Pl yell-2,3pPT
 "you all yelled"
 - + if collective marker *-nu* is followed by subject-as-agent clitic *-mí*, *-mí* becomes low and a following verb stem becomes assimilated to all L (except LH stems)
 - e.g. *áá-nu-mí ira-me* > *áánumi irame*
 man-COLL-SubjAsAgent cook-2,3pPT
 "all of the men cooked it"
 - + basic high tone stems turn to all low if they are noun objects and follow basic low free pronouns
 - e.g. *nimi áá ná-lepaape* > *nimi aa nalepaape*
 you all man eat-IMP
 "you all eat the man"

- Rule 3
 - + a basic low tone becomes a high tone when following a high tone
 - e.g. *go roga-a* > *go roгаа*
 that (near) bind-IMP
 "bind that one there"
 - só roga-a* > *só róгаа*
 that (above) bind-IMP
 "bind that one up there"

2.2.2 Dissimilation

- any basic L stem is very unstable, especially if adjacent to another basic L stem
- e.g. *aani-nu pa-me* > *aaninú páme*
 husband-COLL do-2,3pPT
 "all of the husbands did it"
- basic L reverses most frequently all its tones to H
- Rule 1: n-B-H... -> L... / n-B-H *-mé* _

+ all basic H in a noun turn to basic L when following a noun stem with final basic H and -*mé* affixed to it

e.g. *áá-mé kópó tá-a* > *áámé kopo taa*
 man-SubjAsAgent plate hit-3sPT
 “the man hit the plate”

- Rule 2: L... -> H... / x(-*mé*) _

+ all lows in a word turn to all highs after a stem of any word class which can occur with the clitic -*mé*

e.g. *aani akena púa-a* > *aani ákéná púa*
 husband eel go-3sPT
 “the husband went to the eel”

áá-mé akena tá-a > *áámé ákéná táá*
 man-SubjAsAgent eel hit-3sPT

- Rule 3: HL becomes LH if

+ it is followed by -*mé*

e.g. *áápidi-mé aani tá-a* > *aapidími ááni táá*
 stone axe-SubjAsAgent husband hit-3sPT
 “the stone axe hit the husband”

+ it is preceded by a basic H in a noun (which may be followed by -*mé*)

e.g. *áá-mé áápidi tá-a* > *áámé aapidí táá*
 man-SubjAsAgent stone axe hit-3sPT
 “the man hit the stone axe”

áá áápidi púa-a > *áá aapidí púa*
 man stone axe go-3sPT
 “the man went to the stone axe”

3. Morpho-Syntax

3.1 Fusion

- most suffixes assimilate to the tones of the stem

e.g. *moge-su* > *mogesu*
 try-1sRP
 “some time ago I tried it”

rádépé-su > *rádépésú*
 scrape-1sRP
 “some time ago I scraped it”

- exceptions:

+ suffixes that are LH

+ medial verb suffixes

e.g. *aani yalá-a akena roгаа-ria* > *aani yalóa ákéná roгааria*
 husband yell-ssCONS eel bind-3sPT
 “the husband yelled and then bound the eel”

akena changes to high although it is adjacent to -*a* which is interpreted as basic low

final tone of medial suffix actualizes as mid, maybe because of the clause boundary

- inceptive aspect affix *-ba*

+ morpho-phonemic rules apply to *-ba*, not to the verb base

+ behaves as if belonging to verb class A (even if affixed to a verb base from a different inflectional class)

e.g. *ira-ba-a* > *iraboa*

cook-INC-ssCONS

“having begun to cook it and...”

+ some other aspect affixes attach following the tense suffix

e.g. *ira-wa-de* > *irawade*

cook-1sPT-PUNCT(iliar)

“I cooked it”

3.2 Non-Adjacent Allomorphy

none

3.3 Infixation, Circumfixation, Simulfixation

none

3.4 Reduplication

none

3.5 Clitics and Particles

- particles

+ function at sentence- or clause-level as subordinators or connectors

+ subordinators: free forms

e.g. *épalia rábú épé ta*
he will come when good it is

“When he comes it will be good.”

+ connectors: clitics or the affirmative verb *ya* “to be” plus a clitic, depending on type of connected clauses

e.g. *ora láe-pare napálua*
true you said-but I will not go

“You spoke true but I will not go.”

ora yapare napálua

true however I will not go

“True, however I will not go.”

- clitics

+ “do not occur as free forms” (p. 30)

+ “cannot be considered as affixes because at least some of them can occur, in combination with each other, as words” (p. 30)

+ “On the phonological realm, clitics in combination with stems or each other, as well as any V which is not /a/ or /aa/ but which is followed by one of them, have audible transition points.” (p. 12)

+ have “independent perturbation rules” (p. 25)

+ cause perturbations themselves rather than simply assimilating to the tone of the stem

+ some mark noun phrases that expound certain functions, e.g. Subject-as-Agent or Object-as-Location

e.g. *adaa áá-mé*
big man-SubjAsAgent
“the big man”

adaa áá láápo-mé
big man two-SubjAsAgent
“the two big men”

- some act on word-level, e.g. collective *-nu* or information question marker *aa-*

e.g. *aa-áá*
Q-man
“what man?”

4. Other Questions

4.1 Unstressed Vowels

Nothing happens.

4.2 Word-Word Combinations

- compound stems

+ borders signaled by change in pitch at the edge and/or “plus juncture” (p. 12)

+ sometimes show interaction of tones of fused morphemes

+ sometimes show interaction with final tones of adjacent stems

- compounds

+ compound nouns have same properties as simple nouns, e.g. same perturbation patterns

+ some show basic tones of single constituents

e.g. *íníááa* "face" (*íní* "eyes", *ááa* "mouth")

+ some show internal perturbation

e.g. *kíóraa* "palm" (*kí* "hand", *óraa* "touch")

ááoráá "sole" (*aa* "foot", *óraa* "touch")

+ "It has not been possible to deal with compounds, especially the more involved ones." (p. 18)

4.3 Bipartite Stems

none

4.4 Periphrastic Morphology

none

4.5 Pre- and Postpositions

none